

Research Data Exchange (RDX)

Project Results

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The Research Data Exchange is one of the use-cases in the Amsterdam Data Exchange (AMdEX) field lab project (2021-2023). The AMdEX field lab project is co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund (EDRF) and the Province of North-Holland.

This paper is an extended version of section 4.3 of “AMdEX Reference Architecture”, by L. Thomas van Binsbergen et al., which is publicly available with DOI [10.5281/zenodo.10565915](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10565915).

1 Summary

As part of the AMdEX Fieldlab project, SURF has built a prototype of the Research Data Exchange (RDX), a tool that allows the enforcement of different data sharing conditions for (confidential) datasets. The current RDX prototype is able to connect Figshare, a data publication platform used at the University of Amsterdam, to SANE from SURF (an algorithm-to-data tool). It was used to engage with potential users about what sort of data sharing condition they think should be enforced. The Research Institute for Child Development and Education (RICDE) of the University of Amsterdam (UvA) acted as a pilot user.

Section 2 describes the problem statement, while the, goal, design principles and prototype are explained in further sections. Section 6 lists some of the possible and desired data sharing conditions. Section 7 concludes with the main take aways from interviews with potential users.

2 The Open Science Dilemma

The Research Institute for Child Development and Education (RICDE) employs about 200 researchers in the field of social and behavioural sciences. Most of the research analysis is based on newly collected datasets, and most of these datasets are confidential in order to protect the privacy of the participants in the studies.

The Netherlands strives to Open Science, where scientific knowledge (scientific publications, research data, meta-data, educational resources, software and source code, and open hardware) is openly available¹, and where datasets are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). However, this gives rise to the Open Science Dilemma: how to make confidential datasets accessible?

On the one hand Open Science advocates for the dissemination of as much data as possible on an open platform to promote scientific progress, enable transparency, and allow for the replication of analyses. Additionally, given that scientific research is often funded with public money, it is important to make research results and data accessible to the public. On the other hand, legal and sovereignty issues can limit the extent to which data can be openly shared. It is important to maintain control over confidential datasets, which can entail legal issues such as ownership and copyright, confidentiality of personal data, restrictions on informed consent letters, purpose limitations, bans on dual use, and prohibitions on resale.

3 Goals

The Research Data Exchange (RDX) is a prototype that automates the process of making data available for re-use. This prototype served two purposes:

¹ See e.g. NPOS. (2022). Open Science 2030 in the Netherlands: NPOS2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433767>

- Get experience on the usability of connecting a data repository to a trusted research environment, and get an understanding of the different roles involved (data owner, data provider, data steward, data consumer, service provider);
- Get insight in which data sharing conditions are desired in practice.

4 Design Principles

4.1 Secure Analysis Environment (SANE)

The prototype makes use of the Secure Analysis Environment (SANE), offered by SURF. SANE is a Trusted Research Environment (TRE) developed by SURF in collaboration with ODISSEI and CLARIAH, and sponsored by PDI-SSH. ODISSEI and CLARIAH are two organizations that provide research infrastructures for social sciences and humanities, respectively. SANE is a variant of a compute-to-data archetype, the "Sharing Data via Trusted Third Party (TTP)" archetype. In SANE, SURF acts as a third party which performs the computation under control of the data owner, with the software provider (also) the data consumer.

The figure below gives a visual representation of the different actors in this archetype.

In the "Sharing Data via Trusted Third Party (TTP)" archetype, the Data Provider provides the data, and the Algorithm Provider provides the algorithm. The algorithm is run in a secure container at a Service Provider, and the output of this computation is first verified by the data provider before to ensure it does not contain any confidential information, before this output is released to the Algorithm Provider.

A Trusted Research Environment such as SANE provides control to the data owner, because the data is only made available in a secure environment. It cannot be downloaded. Hence, it allows for the re-use of confidential data while ensuring its confidentiality. However, the current process requires a manual effort each time a researcher wishes to utilize a confidential dataset provided by someone else. In this process, the researcher, acting as the data consumer, must locate the dataset on existing data repositories (e.g., DANS or OSF). Unfortunately, the lack of a download option for confidential datasets means that the only available course of action is to communicate via email with the data owner and hope that they are willing to either provide the

dataset for download or make it accessible within a secure analysis environment. This method is not only tedious and time-consuming, but it also places a burden on the data owners.

Manual workflow for re-use of confidential data by a researcher.

4.2 Research Data Exchange

In contrast to the current situation, the research data exchange splits the workflow in two parts: one for the data owners and one for the data consumers.

With RDX, a data owner can specify the data sharing conditions for each dataset, and make the dataset available for re-use. This only needs to be done once, at the same time the (meta-)data is published on a data repository to make it findable.

Publication workflow (for data owners).

If desired by the data owner, there is an option to perform manual output verification for each analysis conducted by a data consumer, as well as access the records of previous analyses conducted on the dataset. It is up to the data owner to either perform manual output verification for each use, or to only verify logged activities in case there is an indication that a data consumer did not adhere to the agreed data sharing conditions. This level of control is crucial as it empowers the data owner to maintain complete oversight of the confidential dataset and its usage.

Re-use workflow (for data consumers)

When a researcher is interested in re-using a dataset, they can still locate the (meta)data on an existing repository. However, instead of engaging in negotiations with the data owner for access, the RDX prototype automatically enforces access permissions. Depending on the data sharing conditions, the data consumer must first prove its affiliation (e.g., be part of an existing research community) and agree to the designated sharing conditions (e.g., non-commercial use or citation requirements). Once these conditions are met, the data consumer can proceed to download the data or conduct analyses within a secure analysis environment. The specific actions allowed are contingent upon the data sharing conditions established by the data owner in the publication workflow.

5 Prototype

Based on the High Level Architecture², a prototype was build for the Research Data Exchange (RDX). The screenshots below show the re-use workflow for a data consumer.

² Mike Kotsur, High Level Architecture for version 2 (MVP2) of the Research Data Exchange (RDX) prototype, 6 June 2022

In the top-left screenshot, a potential data consumer finds a confidential dataset in an existing repository. For the prototype, we used a sample dataset in the UvA Figshare publication platform³. While the file(s) are not publicly available, there is an option to click on the link to the RDX landing page for this dataset. This leads to the page in the top-right screenshot, which presents the datasharing conditions to the user. A user can only proceed, by agreeing to the stipulated data sharing conditions, and entering their name and email address. If this is done and submitted, the page shows that the request was submitted (bottom-left screenshot). It tells the user that a virtual machine (VM) is spun up, and that this will be accessible in about half an hour. After the VM is initialized, the requesters received an email with instructions how to access the VM with remote desktop, the confidential dataset and data analysis tools. The remote desktop environment is provided by SANE and is depicted in the bottom-right corner. This VM does not have internet access, except to a dropbox folder in SURF Research Drive, where the user can upload the result of the analysis. The content of this drop box is either shared with the data owner, or the data consumer directly. If it is shared with the data owner, the data owner can optionally proceed to verify that the result does not contain any confidential information and if not, share the result with the data consumer. Alternatively, the output can be shared with the data consumer without manual verification. In that case, the output is still logged for optional verification later. The prototype did not contain any automatic output verification, because that was deemed too unreliable. If manually verification of the output is required or not is highly debated. Some regard it as an essential part to ensure privacy of the subjects of a study. Other regard it as personal interference which does not scale and ultimately will make it unworkable.

6 Data Sharing Conditions

Based on small-scale interviews with potential users, and earlier experience, we can list the following data sharing conditions. The list is roughly ordered from most important to least important.

- Verify identity and affiliation
- Sign data sharing conditions
 - Do not redistribute the dataset
 - Purpose-binding; dataset may only be used to answer specific (pre-approved) research questions
 - Give credit when data is re-used
 - Involvement in the analysis and co-authorship
- Verification of the analysis output before releasing the output
- Verification that the resulting paper does not contain confidential information
- Analyse in a secure analysis environment only
- Only allow verified algorithms for analysis

The prototype was able to enforce the following conditions:

- Verify email address
- Sign data sharing conditions

³ Emma E. Schreurs, Test Data RDX MVP 2, https://uvaauas.figshare.com/articles/dataset/Test_Data_RDX_MVP_2/24235066 (sample dataset may be removed)

- Only make the dataset available after automatic verification of the above conditions
- No download allowed, analyse in a secure analysis environment only (optional)
- Verification of the analysis output before releasing the output (optional)

In total, five combinations of data sharing conditions are supported:

- Make available for download, after verification of email address and signing data sharing conditions;
- Make available for processing in a "tinker" secure analysis environment, after verification of email address and signing data sharing conditions, either with or without verification of the output by the data provider;
- Make available for processing in a "blind" secure analysis environment, after verification of email address and signing data sharing conditions, either with or without verification of the output by the data provider.

The tinker- and blind secure analysis environment were provided by the SANE pilot. The difference between the two is that the tinker SANE spins up a job submission process, where the data is made available in a remote desktop Windows environment that contains the data, and data processing tools (for the prototype R Studio and Jupyter notebook). For the blind SANE, the data consumer must specify a Python script that is executed in a VM where the data is made available. In both cases, the VM does not allow network connections, so it is not possible to upload the dataset elsewhere. The result of the analysis can only be uploaded to a specific output, where the result is logged and is optional verified by the data owner before it is released.

7 Conclusion

Six interviews with potential users were conducted, five with researchers from the University of Amsterdam, one with a researcher from Utrecht University. These people were selected based on their interest in the topic, so the sample was not representative of an average population of researchers.

Based on these interviews and demonstrations with the prototype, we came to the following conclusions.

Knowledge about PETs is not widespread. We run a few tests, and got positive responses, in particular from the University of Amsterdam. However, the technology is still new, and the concept of data-reuse, without data download is still novel. We found that the SANE pilot is getting noted by data stewards and digital competence centers. However, most individual researchers do not yet know about this possibility, let alone other privacy enhancing technologies (PETs) that are available nowadays. By extension, the RDX prototype was new as well for most researchers. The prototype proved to be of benefit as a conversation starter, that helps explain the possibilities that PETs offer.

Guide researchers to the right place. For some researchers, the distinction between a data repository, data publication platform, data analysis platform and place where data is stored is not clear. A researcher who heard about SANE may visit it, and expect there a list of available

datasets. Researchers need to be educated and guided to the correct place where these datasets are listed.

Concerns about storing sensitive data at a trusted third party. Some interviewees expressed concern that not all data owners want to store their sensitive data at SURF, even temporarily during the analysis only. The prevalence of this concern is unknown, but in those cases, an option to run an analysis at the data provider itself (instead of at a third party) may be a solution. One software tool that support such archetype is Vantage6.

Data owners and Data stewards both feel responsible. A researcher who creates a dataset is often referred to as a “data owner”, despite that there is no legal concept of “ownership” of data. They often spend a significant amount of work collecting the data, and all feel personally responsible for protecting the privacy of the participants of the study they performed. That said, the legal obligation to protect privacy sensitive data lies with the data controller and data processor, thus with the research institution rather than the individual researchers who created the dataset. This responsibility (along with responsibilities on e.g. data provenance and data preservation) is often delegated to a data steward (a supporting role within the organization, acting as the data provider or data custodian in the prototype).

Data owners and Data stewards both want to be involved. With a technology this new, we found that both the data owners as well as the data steward want to know who is using the data. We anticipate that when this technology is used more extensively, in particular the data steward wants to have a hand-off, mostly overseeing role, and that the data owner want to remain involved, if only as to seek potential collaborations with the people interested in their datasets.

For data owners, trust in the data consumer is paramount. That trust does not simply come from an affiliation, like another university. At first glance, this seems like a subjective criterion, but upon further questioning, it could be stipulated as a fellow researcher who has published in high-impact journals before.

Logging may be used as alternative to verification. The prototype allows for the option that the data owner or the data provider verifies that the result of each analysis no longer contains any personal information. However, neither party seemed to view this as the ideal situation. Data stewards seem to feel that logging of the actions and output is sufficient. That would take away the burden of manually checking of each analysis, and still provides a means to correct data consumers that do not adhere to the data sharing conditions, even if it is after the fact. The data owners also seem to trust the consumer with the data, and do not need to check the output of each analysis. However, they do want to check the resulting publication(s) before they are published, since any recognizable data in a publication is a severe breach in privacy.

Data owners may want to be involved in follow-up studies. Whereas data stewards want a more distant role, data owners clearly want to be more involved with any follow-up study. Most interviewees indicated that they prefer to actively prefer to collaborate with a requester when they request access to their data, rather than simply let them re-use it on their own. To facilitate this, a data publication platform may want to add an optional feature to contact the data owner directly, without mandating this contact.

The prototype is not designed for protect against malicious actors. This is acceptable by data owners and data providers. That does not mean there is no concern, but the concern mostly comes from (a) risk of leaking identifiable information in a publication; or (b) risk of reputation damage, because a data consumer makes errors in the analysis or draws a faulty conclusion; or (c) risk of reputation damage, because the compute-to-data archetype is not well understood, and the general public does not distinguish between re-use of data and redistribution of data.

A secure analysis environment may be relevant to larger data providers. For individual use cases, most data owners prefer individually checking the reputation of the data consumer, and if sound, let them simply download the data. For example, if they share the data with their colleagues. Only when data is more frequently reused (for example, the results of a large cohort study), a more elaborate process for granting access may become necessary, and may involve a secure analysis environment.

Automatic publication of datasets is not yet solved. In the prototype, the computation was done by a trusted third party, SURF, who had to be trusted by the data provider to protect the data. However, this also means there must be a way for the data provider to make the confidential data sets available to the third party. In the prototype, this was a manual process. For actual deployment, this must be automated.

Researchers are opportunistic. The willingness to pay for data differs a lot per researcher. Some don't see an issue, and say the cost can simply be added to the budget in the project proposal. Others say that they will never pay, for the reason that they do not know the usefulness before they can see the data. In all cases, it seems that the real burden is in finding a high-quality data set, and quickly assessing if it is worth further investigation. Publication of codebooks, samples made with synthetic data, and a smooth process can help with this assessment.

Need for a secure collaboration environment. A stable, secure and user-friendly VRE (virtual research environment) may be beneficial. For example, when coding of video into an annotated transcript, this would be useful for coders to use. Another example is a smaller institution that does have their own secure storage platform, but not the tools to give access to partners who work elsewhere. In that case, a secure environment where the data can not be downloaded from would be useful.

Store intermediate results. It is not uncommon to redo an analysis later; for example, a reviewer or supervisor may ask questions about an analysis that warrant a further analysis of the data. In this case, it should be possible to quickly resume the original secure analysis environment without repeating the request process or repeating earlier work.

Export intermediate results. Some data consumers may want to publish enriched data sets as intermediate results.

Filtering of the data. Some data owners may want to create a subset of the data with only the details required to perform an analysis, before the data is made available to a data analyst.

Required Software. The interviewees in social sciences use the following software in their analysis, and expect this to be available in a secure analysis environment: R Studio, mPlus, SPSS, or JASP for statistical analysis. It seemed that R Studio was gaining popularity over commercial offerings such as MPlus and SPSS, but this was not a universal opinion, and the number of

interviews was not large enough to draw a definitive conclusion. In addition to these tools, some researchers may do other specific task that requires other software. For example, PLINK to analyze genome data, or Excel and MPC-HC or VLC for transcribing video.

8 Future Work

As an addendum: some of the concepts discussed in this document were submitted as a input for further developments of what is called a “Data Access Broker”, in a collaboration between ODISSEI and SURF.